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Python for Engineers Concept Inventory (PECI): Contextualized assessment of programming skills for engineering undergraduates

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ABSTRACT

A key outcome of Engineering Education is computing skills for industry 4.0. The curriculum must address an increasing reliance on model-based design, simulation, and algorithmic data processing. Python is a popular, in-demand language; exhaustive online resources and tutorials exist, challenging educators to make assessment robust to online plagiarism, and to make instruction contextually relevant to engineering. How do engineering educators develop, measure, and evaluate engineering students programming skills, accelerate their learning, and improve instruction effectiveness? A Concept Inventory (CI) is a powerful standardised assessment instrument to answer this question and its development and validation is an active research topic. We present a Python for Engineers CI (PECI) which assesses concepts, and errors observed in learners through 250 Multiple Choice Questions (MCQs). It is evaluated by embedding it into an introductory undergraduate module, whose pedagogy includes contextualised learning and auto-graded interactive computing laboratory notebooks. Using a mixed-methods approach on learning data from a student cohort (n=68), we validate Peci through student learning gains, reliability analysis and qualitative feedback. Items are shown to differentiate high and low performing students, and each item contributes to assessment reliability. The work is of value to engineering educators wishing to develop standardised assessment instruments for computing skills.

1 INTRODUCTION

How can engineering students' ability and performance in programming be measured accurately and reliably, and what pedagogical practices can enhance their performance? A key part of Engineering Education is the development of computing skills. These are used for design and analytical work; electrical and computer engineers traditionally have the highest need, require design skills for programming software for desktop applications, and firmware for hardware devices using procedural

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languages such as C. Other engineering disciplines such as chemical, mechanical and civil engineering have lesser need, but still make extensive use of analytical software for data and simulation that frequently requires interactive computing tools e.g. Matlab & Simulink. There is an increasing move in Engineering towards Industry 4.0 which promises a model-based design approach in all disciplines as engineering products and solutions undergo detailed simulation before production, with increasing reliance on algorithmic data processing, machine learning and automation. These trends create the requirement to increase programming in engineering curricula. According to the IEEE, Python is now the most popular and in-demand of all programming languages².

Online access to learning python programming skills is ubiquitous; exhaustive online resources and tutorials not specific to engineering exist of varying quality. This means that teaching programming in engineering programme is straightforward, if not particularly redundant or efficient – a programming module can be compiled from existing online materials, texts and exercises. However, this simplicity and easy-of-entry carries risks for the engineering educator: the challenge of making any programming assessments robust to online search, adding enough value to what already exists, and making the learning context entirely relevant to engineering. Furthermore, a key issue in teaching programming is assessing student output – programming is an open-ended, creative endeavour; a variety of solutions with very different coding styles and structures can produce the same result. How can assessment of this creative skill be standardised while simultaneously giving students the freedom to code how they want?

In this work we answer these questions by presenting the Python for Engineers Concept Inventory (PECI), which standardises assessment, provides engineering contextualisation, and affords analytics to measure and improve an engineer's programming skills. This article proceeds as follows. In Section 2, we describe programming pedagogies and CIs. In section 3 we describe PECI's embedding into an undergraduate module. In section 4, PECI is evaluated in terms of measured learning gain, assessment reliability, and qualitative feedback. In section 5 we discuss our findings and future work.

2 TEACHING ENGINEERING PROGRAMMING SKILLS

2.1 Pedagogical Interventions

What pedagogical practices can enhance programming skill? Programming is widely reported to be a complex cognitive skill which is difficult to master, resulting in low student engagement and drop-outs. The majority of education studies in teaching programming report case studies that investigate novice computer science cohorts. Given similar entry requirements to Higher Education degree programmes, it is reasonable to assume that CS cohorts share many similarities with early-year

² <https://spectrum.ieee.org/at-work/innovation/the-2018-top-programming-languages>

engineering cohorts and consequently their findings can be considered as valid in engineering contexts. Interventions to improve effectiveness reported include collaboration, peer support and group work, content change, preliminary courses, gamification, grade-weightings, and contextualisation [1]. The most popular foci in student-oriented education research studies is on content and measuring student ability, for teaching-oriented studies it is the tools and activities, and for assessment-oriented studies it is the theories and models [2]. Our work focuses on all three aspects, with a primary focus on measuring student ability through assessment.

2.2 Concept Inventories as a standardised assessment model.

How can engineering students' ability and performance in programming be measured accurately and reliably? To reliably measure student ability, a concept inventory (CI) is a standardised assessment tool that defines a set of key constructs and accompanying assessments used to assess a student's conceptual understanding of a subject. Identifying which concepts are key is the subject of much debate in the literature; the optimal set that minimises the volume of teaching materials while maximising student learning are known as threshold concepts. These concepts possess one more specific characteristic: they transform subject understanding irreversibly, reveal connections and relationships, define the disciplinary boundaries, and are troublesome for students [3].

One of the earliest CIs is the physics Force Concept Inventory (FCI) [4], which was demonstrated to show a reliable assessment of student understanding. Since then, Engineering Education has proposed a variety of CIs [5]. Identifying the threshold concepts within these CIs is considered important for efficiency yet difficult; much identification is done through the teacher's subject understanding with student performances highlighting the troublesome concepts. However, it is noted that troublesome concepts may be due to lack of student motivation rather than difficulty [6].

In the framework proposed by [7], a CI should be validated to ensure it measures students overall and specific understandings and propensity for misconceptions and errors. This is achieved using several techniques including classical test theory (CTT), Item Response theory (IRT), factor analyses, and hybrid approaches. CTT enables the difficulty, discriminability, reliability and coherence of the CI to be determined. IRT enables each concept item's difficulty to be evaluated against student proficiency, while factor analyses help to identify underlying hidden factors that relate elements in the CI.

2.3 Misconceptions as common programming errors

For an engineering programming CI, how are its items determined? There is a distinction between programming concept items and programming error items. Errors arise from misunderstandings of the programming concepts or misuse/understanding of programming language syntax. A good source of misconceptions comes from observing novice programmers in practice. Early work in [8] observing programmers

identified three common errors relating to students: 1) parallelism, where line-by-line sequential interpretation is usurped and previous statements are incorrectly identified as active; 2) Intentionality, where sequential interpretation is mediated by goals that are inferred by the program due to other statements; 3) Egocentrism, where it is assumed the computer does and knows more than that made explicit within the code. Decades of subsequent studies have yielded comprehensive lists of misconceptions spawned from these three errors and amalgamated from all languages e.g. 162 misconceptions [9]. However, these larger lists are unwieldy and not all items can be reasonably tested or are relevant to specific languages. Specific to python, work in [10] and [11] identifies a more manageable 26 and 25 programming errors items respectively.

3 PECE STRUCTURE AND MODULE EMBEDDING

3.1 PECE Structure

The PECE structure is given in Table 1. It has 15 concept items taken from the glossaries of a standard reference python text book with each chapter constituting a specific concept item (column 1) [12]. There are 24 programming error items observed in previous work (column 2) [10][11]. 250 Multiple Choice Questions (MCQs) are devised from these items to test student’s ability to understand concepts or error relating to python code written for a specific Engineering context (column 3). An example MCQ from the CI is shown in *Fig 1*.

What is wrong with this code fragment?

```
var = 10
equilibrium = 5
timer = 0
while var > 0:
    print(f'Angular speed adjusted to : {var} rad/s')
    var -= 1
    timer += 1
    if var == equilibrium:
        break
    print(f'Angular speed now at equilibrium at {var} rad/s After {timer} seconds')
```

- There is an f outside each string.
- This is an infinite loop
- Variables assigned outside loop
- Indentation of second print statement should be the same as if statement
- break statement should be after print statement.

Fig. 1. Example PECE MCQ

Table 1. PECEI structure. Each question in the inventory is derived from a combination of Concepts, Errors, and the Engineering context.

Programming Concepts [12]	Programming Errors [10][11]	Engineering Contextualisation
C1: The Program	A: Invalid names	Mathematics
C2: Variables	B: Left-to-right assignments	Fluid dynamics
C3: Expressions	C: Assignments in expressions	Digital Electronics
C4: Statements	D: Expressions as parameters	Analogue Electronics
C5: Functions	E: Literal values instead of variables	Structural Analysis
C6: Conditionals	F: Extra or missing spaces	Mechanical Design
C7: Recursion	G: Invalid else-statements	Materials.
C8: Fruitful functions	H: Missing or extra quotation marks	
C9: Iteration	I: Division and modulo	
C10: Strings	J: Invalid use of the and-operator.	
C11: Lists	K: Wrong or extra keyword.	
C12: Dictionaries	L: Incorrect structure.	
C13: Tuples	M: Unbalanced parentheses and brackets	
C14: Files	N: Misspelled names or keywords.	
C15: Classes	O: Using keywords as names	
	P: Using assignment instead of comparison.	
	Q: Misspelled operators.	
	R: Unterminated string literal.	
	S: Missing colon, comma or operator.	
	T: Invalid Indentation.	
	U: Code after a break statement.	
	V: Call without parentheses.	
	W: Useless computations.	
	X: Useless comparison.	

3.2 Module Embedding

PECEI is designed to be independent of the teaching and learning activities. In this case-study, PECEI is validated in a 10-credit module designed for 1st and 2nd year undergraduate engineering students that assumes little or no prior programming experience. Fig. 2 shows how PECEI is embedded into the module. PECEI tests are administered throughout the module – an identical pre- and post-learning test, practice tests, and a final summative class test. The student performance data from pre- and post- learning test results enables learning gain to be measured for each student. Analysis and Practice improvement is afforded from this measured learning.

Fig. 2. Embedding PECEI into the case-study Module

3.3 Lab Pedagogy

In our case study, python is learned through contextualised laboratory exercises before (pre-lab) and after (post-lab). The exercises use interactive programming notebooks³ and automatic marking of programming code using the NB Grader plugin⁴. This means that rather than learning to program by writing source code files, students learn to code by writing snippets inline to solve problems which are automatically checked for errors by using a plugin for the notebook that can check code for correct output. The problem-solving aspects include designing digital logic schemes, signal processing and machine learning exercises. Notably, the learning materials are independent of PECl i.e. they are not directly teaching students to answer one of its MCQs.

4 EVALUATION

4.1 Student Learning Gain

Student learning gain is measured by comparing the pre-learning and post-learning student performance against PECl. 50 MCQs are pre-selected from the 250 MCQs in PECl to ensure a broad coverage of concepts and programming errors. The test is administered to the student cohort at the start and the end of the learning in timed examination conditions and is formative. For the student cohort in this study (N=68), the pre-learning PECl scores range from 12% to 53% with an average of 29% and standard deviation of 5.09. The post-learning PECl scores range from 42% to 93% with an average of 73% and standard deviation of 8.62. This demonstrates that PECl measures knowledge improvement from students undertaking learning activities where students are expected to show learning gains, with the potential for different learning gains to be compared across different cohorts and teaching methods.

To better understand the learning gain, item difficulty is calculated by dividing the mean score by the maximum possible, producing a value between 0 and 1 for each item, with 1 indicating high scores. Item discrimination is calculated by point-biserial correlation, which compares individual scores against those for the overall test, producing a value for each CI item between -1.0 and +1.0. Negative values are undesirable and indicate that high scorers are wrong. Positive values are desirable and indicate that high-scorers are scoring right, and that low scorers are scoring wrong.

Fig. 3 shows the comparison between pre- and post- learning difficulty vs discrimination. As expected, for the pre-learning test the majority of the PECl items (diamonds) prove to be difficult; no item has a discriminability greater than 0.6. There are also several concepts with negative discriminability which suggest gaps in student knowledge regardless of ability.

The post-learning test results show a vast improvement. Most items have higher difficulty scores indicating better cohort performance, and this is positively correlated

³ <https://www.jupyter.org>

⁴ <https://nbgrader.readthedocs.io/en/stable/#>

with item discriminability indicating good separation between high and low achievers. Comparison of the pre-learning negative linear trend lines and post-learning positive linear trend line highlight this desired improvement.

Fig. 3. Comparing Difficulty vs Discriminability of PECEI between pre- and postlearning demonstrating cohort improvement.

4.2 PECEI Reliability

PECEI is evaluated by adopting the first stage of the framework proposed in [7] - employing Classical Test theory (CTT) to measure reliability. Test scores are analysed using SPSS software. Reliability is reported separately for PECEI concept items and errors items

4.2.1 Error items

For the 24 programming errors types, Cronbach's alpha showed the test comfortably met the criteria for acceptable reliability (>0.7) at $\alpha = 0.82$. There were mostly low correlations ($r < 0.3$) between error types (Fig. 4), which suggests that each item is less likely to represent the same underlying concept and thus be potentially redundant.

Alpha remains high regardless of the item deleted, ranging from 0.80 to 0.82. Analysis of the mean and standard deviations for each item revealed certain errors are easily

detected and corrected by students e.g. B, while others e.g. E, are not. However, all but one item results in a decrease in the alpha if deleted. The one exception - error X - would increase the alpha to $\alpha = 0.83$ if not included. However, this difference is negligible.

Further evidence of the value of all programming error items in the CI comes from the inter-item correlation matrix (Fig. 4), which have low correlations ($r < 0.3$) between error items. This suggests that there is no underlying single programming “error” concept could make individual items in the CI potentially redundant.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X
A	1.0	0.6	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.0	-0.1	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0
B	0.6	1.0	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.0	-0.1	0.3	0.2	0.0	0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	-0.1	0.2
C	0.2	0.3	1.0	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.1
D	0.2	0.4	0.1	1.0	0.5	0.4	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
E	0.2	0.3	0.0	0.5	1.0	0.4	-0.1	0.2	0.0	-0.1	0.2	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1
F	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.4	1.0	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0
G	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.1	-0.1	0.1	1.0	0.1	0.4	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1	-0.1
H	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.1	1.0	0.3	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	-0.1	0.0
I	0.0	0.0	0.4	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.4	0.3	1.0	0.5	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.0	0.0
J	-0.1	-0.1	0.4	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.6	0.2	0.5	1.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.4	0.2	0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.3	-0.1
K	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.2	-0.1	1.0	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.1	-0.1
L	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.1	-0.1	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	1.0	0.4	0.5	0.3	-0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.4	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.2
M	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.4	1.0	0.5	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.2	0.6	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.1
N	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2	-0.1	0.1	0.5	0.5	1.0	0.2	0.0	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.0	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.4
O	0.2	-0.1	0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.4	0.4	0.0	0.3	0.3	0.2	1.0	0.4	0.5	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.1
P	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.5	0.2	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.4	1.0	0.4	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.0	0.0
Q	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.5	0.4	1.0	0.5	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.4
R	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.3	-0.1	0.3	-0.1	0.2	0.4	0.1	0.3	0.5	1.0	0.2	0.2	0.4	-0.1	0.2	-0.1
S	0.2	0.0	0.3	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.4	0.6	0.5	0.2	0.0	0.3	0.2	1.0	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.3	-0.1
T	0.2	0.0	0.2	-0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.4	0.1	0.3	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.5	1.0	0.4	0.2	0.5	-0.1
U	0.1	0.2	0.4	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.3	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.4	1.0	0.3	0.2	0.2
V	-0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.4	-0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	1.0	0.5	0.7
W	0.0	-0.1	0.2	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.1	0.2	0.3	0.1	-0.1	0.3	0.2	0.4	0.0	0.5	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.2	0.5	1.0	0.3
X	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.4	0.1	0.0	0.4	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.2	0.7	0.3	1.0

Fig. 4 Inter-item correlation matrix for PECl error items A-X. For item descriptions, see Table 1.

4.2.2 Concept items

For the 15 programming concept items in the CI, 11 are assessed via 26 questions with some concepts assessed multiple times due to their greater depth. Cronbach’s alpha shows the test fall marginally short of acceptable reliability (>0.7) at $\alpha = 0.68$. Removing items from the test produces a range of alphas between 0.64, 0.72. However, test reliability is easily made acceptable (>0.7) by removing one of two MCQs from either item 1 or 4.

4.3 Qualitative Student Feedback.

Students are questioned on the methods used to teaching programming in the module. Overall there is a tacit approval to using the CI MCQ to assess skills alongside developing skills using laboratory exercises. Notably, most of the comments focus on the teaching e.g. lab exercises rather than the PECl tests. A selection of the responses is shown in Table 2. Notably, comments validate the underlying ethos of the module, that programming is an open-ended concept learned by doing.

Table 2. Selection of qualitative feedback given by students

Question	Response
The thing I found most helpful.	<i>Helped to develop my programming skills, The way it was structured. Provides a very linear, easy to understand representation of how much you understand; Good for basic concepts.</i>
The most useful thing/skill I learned	<i>There is no unique answer to any program / solution; I feel like I could attempt my own work in the Python language now; Debugging ability.</i>
The thing that most changed the way I learned	<i>Learning through doing rather than listening. The incremental difficulty helped me break-down problems into smaller problems; The interactive nature of the notebook material.</i>
What made learning most effective for me	<i>Building up the difficulty. I wouldn't have understood the content nearly as well if we were thrown in the deep end right away. Being able to work through the notebooks in small stages over time. Fault-finding the basic stuff in coding.</i>

5 SUMMARY AND AVAILABILITY

Python for Engineering Concept Inventory (PECI) comprises 250 MCQ questions for standardised assessment. It is validated in a best-practice undergraduate module which utilises interactive notebooks to teach python in the context of solving engineering problems. Evaluation results suggest that all PEGI items are reliable, and that the instrument correctly quantitatively measures the improvement in student programming skills before and after an effective learning experience.

While identifying threshold concepts i.e. those that truly transform a student understanding, is an active research topic, the work here highlights that, in practice, this worthy goal can be overstated; a manageable CI of tens of items derived from main subject concepts and observed student errors may often suffice, given an adequate validation via measuring learning gains at the item level and conducting a reliability analysis.

Future work includes further reliability analysis and employing the PEGI as a pre/post learning test in other modules, cohorts, and teaching contexts. Further PEGI details and sample MCQs are available to Engineering Educators via contacting the primary author.

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